

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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Aliyeva Khadija Mohsun
Azerbaijan, Mingachevir State University
Department of Foreign Languages
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EDUCATION AS A BASIC AREA OF HUMAN CAPITAL REPRODUCTION

Алиева Хадиджа Мохсун
Азербайджан, Мингячевирский Государственный Университет
Кафедра иностранных языков

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ КАК БАЗОВАЯ НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВОСПРОИЗВОДСТВА ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА

Abstract.

The growing interest of economic science in human creative abilities and the ways of their activation coincide with the general pattern of development of modern science. From the point of view of economic theory, this implies a transition to the “human” dimension of social life, placing the individual as a producer and consumer at the center of the socio-economic system. This, in turn, requires understanding the role of education and other areas of reproduction of human creative qualities.

The category “human capital” allows us to study many phenomena of a market economy from a unified perspective. According to some scholars, the concept of human capital plays a central role in modern economic analysis. It provides new opportunities for studying problems such as economic growth, income distribution, the place and role of education in social reproduction, the content of the labor process, motivation, etc.

In modern conditions, the requirements of a harmoniously developed personality, which flow from the logic of social and technical progress, come to the fore. Today, the world community is inevitably moving towards the realization of humanistic ideals in education by increasing the social, pedagogical and economic efficiency of its functioning. Social efficiency is expressed in various forms of affirmation of humanism both in society and in the very content and technologies of education as a pedagogical process.

Аннотация.

Возрастающий интерес экономической науки к творческим способностям человека и путям их активации совпадает с общей закономерностью развития современной науки. С точки зрения экономической теории это предполагает переход к «человеческому» измерению общественной жизни, ставя личность как производителя и потребителя в центр социально-экономической системы. Это, в свою очередь, требует понимания роли образования и других сфер воспроизводства творческих качеств человека.

Категория «человеческий капитал» позволяет изучать многие явления рыночной экономики с единой точки зрения. По мнению некоторых ученых, концепция человеческого капитала играет центральную роль в современном экономическом анализе. Это открывает новые возможности для изучения таких проблем, как экономический рост, распределение доходов, место и роль образования в общественном воспроизводстве, содержание трудового процесса, мотивация и т. д.

В современных условиях на первый план выходят потребности гармонично развитой личности, вытекающие из логики социального и технического прогресса. Сегодня мировое сообщество неизбежно движется к реализации гуманистических идеалов образования путем повышения социальной, педагогической и экономической эффективности его функционирования. Социальная эффективность выражается в различных формах утверждения гуманизма как в обществе, так и в самом содержании и технологиях образования как педагогического процесса.

Keywords: *education, human capital, level of economy and culture in society, reproduction, social phenomenon*

Ключевые слова: *образование, человеческий капитал, уровень экономики и культуры общества, воспроизводство, социальное явление.*

The actuality of the study is that education problems are becoming the main economic problems of our time and the near future. At the same time, the study of the role of the education sector in society should be based on an analysis of the essential properties of the educational service as a constitutive basis of the education system. Studying the process of production of an educational service as an economic category from the

perspective of economic theory dictates the need to analyze the problem from the point of view of determining the role and place of this service in the system of reproduction of human capital.

The object of the study is the production and consumption of educational services in the process of forming human capital, and **the subject of the study** is

the economic relations that arise in the process of forming human capital.

The purpose of the study is to form theoretical approaches that allow us to clarify the role of education in the formation of human capital.

Achieving this goal involves solving the **following tasks**:

- determine the features of the production of educational services in the field of education;
- identify the role of educational potential and educational services in the process of reproduction of human capital;
- to clarify the characteristics of the process of formation of the regional market of educational services;
- prove the importance of sources of diversification of education financing.

Education as a social phenomenon is, first of all, an objective social value. The moral, intellectual, scientific, technical, spiritual, cultural and economic potential of any society directly depends on the level of development of the educational sphere.

However, education, having a social nature and historical character, in turn, is determined by the historical type of society that implements this social function. It reflects the tasks of social development, the level of economy and culture in society, the nature of its political and ideological attitudes, since both teachers and students are subjects of social relations [3; 96].

Education as a social phenomenon is a relatively independent system, the function of which is the systematic training and education of members of society, focused on mastering certain knowledge (primarily scientific), ideological and moral values, abilities, skills, norms of behavior, the content of which is ultimately determined socially - the economic and political system of a given society and the level of its material and technical development.

A quick analysis of the recent history of education reform allows us to conclude that beyond the various scenarios for the development of education, as a rule, there were systemic social and mental effects, in the creation of which education participates:

- formation of human identity in a multi-ethnic, multi-confessional and multicultural state;
- social and spiritual consolidation of society;
- ensuring social mobility of the individual, quality and accessibility of education as factors in reducing the risks of social stratification of society;
- construction of social norms of tolerance and trust in each other among representatives of different social groups, religious and national cultures;
- successful socialization of the younger generation;
- increasing the competitiveness of the individual, society and state [1; 127].

Education is the basic sphere of reproduction of human potential, in which a person is formed as an individual. The knowledge gained helps to reveal the essence of human life in society, because worldview, worldview, determination of the place and role of the individual in society, assimilation of the humanitarian foundations of communication, norms of morality and

morality, and the sociocultural development of the individual make a person a part of society. A person's professional training in the educational system lays a solid foundation for professional activity, which realizes personal abilities and his labor potential to the greatest extent. That is why, in the theory of human capital, the level of education of the population is considered as the main component of its value, and education is unanimously recognized as a constant component of labor activity. In addition, modern research proves a stable connection between a person's education and his life expectancy, and, therefore, knowledge as a result of education is important for longevity and has sociobiological significance. Transformational processes in the economy require an innovative approach to the system of training future specialists. Education is inherently an innovative field, since it is based on the constant use of new knowledge produced by scientific institutions and universities. The personnel of the educational system is the most important part of the country's intellectual potential, which, unlike scientists, performs such a social function as educating students, as well as replicating already known theoretical positions, concepts, conclusions and obtaining certain practical skills. These aspects of the educational process are also, to a certain extent, innovative in nature [6].

Increasing the level of education to solving problems in the labor market

Raising the educational level at a higher level is carried out by universities, institutes for advanced training and retraining of personnel. In recent years, there has been a desire among young people to obtain higher qualifications.

The reasons for this situation are most likely the following:

- priority of higher education over secondary vocational education;
- accessibility of higher education associated with the availability of a paid form of education;
- the desire to have a good job and have an alternative choice of workplace;
- the prevailing opinion that a high level of education leads to an increase in income and, in particular, wages [4; 122].

Of course, a person who has a certain amount of knowledge is more competitive and creative. Training in a second specialty makes it possible to reduce the imbalance in the labor market between supply and demand, because a less in demand specialty dictates circumstances that require retraining the employee, that is, obtaining a new specialty that is most in demand in the region. The advantages of the retraining system also include the following:

- training of a second specialty occurs in a shorter period of time;
- obtaining an education using such a system allows you to avoid duplication of disciplines and eliminate a rather large block of general theoretical training;
- the traditional form of lectures has fewer advantages over lectures that have strong feedback, since the teaching persons have certain skills;
- the country's human potential is growing;
- areas of labor application are expanding;

- teaching a theoretical block of disciplines, carried out by the most competent teaching staff, capable of conveying knowledge of a particular subject within the framework of the main ideas of the development of the Azerbaijani state, is most closely linked with the practical skills of students.

In addition, the new specialty, firstly, continuously complements previously received education, and secondly, is a conductor of innovative ideas and technologies. Analyzing the dynamics of statistical data characterizing employment and unemployment, it should be noted that the level of economic activity of the population, that is, the propensity to supply labor, increases in proportion to the level of education, reaching a maximum among persons with higher professional education.

An increase in the level of education leads to an increase in the human potential of the country. Enterprises need knowledgeable, skilled personnel, since new technologies require greater abilities. In this regard, retraining of elderly people will avoid the reduction of this category of workers.

Based on the above, we can conclude that the system of higher and postgraduate education makes it possible to solve pressing problems in the labor market. After all, education outside the context of the labor market loses its meaning, and vocational training is the most important form of individual self-realization in the labor market, in the sphere of labor relations.

In modern conditions, the competitive advantages of economic systems are largely achieved not through natural resources, but through knowledge, information, and innovation, which serve as the basis for the economic growth of countries. This explains the growing interest shown in the development of human capital by leading foreign and domestic scientists.

Despite the contradictory understanding of the structure of human capital, all researchers are unanimous in recognizing the enormous importance of the educational factor, i.e. knowledge, skills, abilities and abilities to perceive them and periodically update them - everything that formal education instills in a person. Many researchers have tried to separate the influence of the education factor on the growth of future income from the influence of health, abilities, and social origin. The results that different scientists have come to regarding the importance of the educational factor are practically the same: the total impact of all factors, with the exception of education, is no more than 40%, therefore 60% of a person's income is explained by the level of his education.

The role of education is not only to increase income levels, but also to expand a person's capabilities and the availability of benefits that make his life more interesting, meaningful, and happy. Education is considered as a necessary benefit for strengthening health and ensuring active longevity of a person, for raising healthier and more prosperous offspring, for preserving a favorable environment, for mutual understanding of different groups of the population.

Countries with developed market economies have long considered the primary form of completed capital

investment in society to be primarily human development, especially for countries that do not have reserves of raw materials and countries with a material base destroyed during the Second World War, such as Taiwan, Korea, Japan, Germany [5].

The concept of human capital is based on two definitions of education - as a resource (human capital itself) and as a system (in which its accumulation occurs), which allows us to build a bridge between the economic and sociological approaches to education. The economic approach considers education as a source of economic growth and evaluates it from the standpoint of economic efficiency through improving the quality of the workforce and labor productivity. The accumulation of human capital occurs both in the process of schooling, which lays down basic knowledge and skills, and during post-school education, aimed at obtaining a specific profession, as well as within the framework of professional activities. Moreover, the skills and knowledge acquired at the previous stages of training increase the efficiency of further investments in human capital and, as a result, provide the opportunity for successful activities in various fields. A higher education institution provides certain professional knowledge and skills, the opportunity to apply them in practice and obtain an initial understanding of the professional labor market in the form of practical training.

But its most important function is the development of general cultural capital, which lays the universal foundation for further professional activity and subsequent development. On a macro scale, a highly educated workforce represents a country's human potential. Thus, the state of the modern education system ultimately determines the development of the country in the coming years. Therefore, it is logical to assert that education is the leading branch of human capital production, the foundation of the future well-being of an individual and the entire society [2; 67]. At its core, the diversity of education systems is a reflection of cultural, social, political, philosophical, religious and economic diversity, which is a unique asset. In addition to specific substantive aspects related to the reflection in the educational process of trends in the universalization of the lifestyle of modern man and the strengthening of regionalization of development, the organizational forms themselves are of great importance, which make it possible to improve educational practice. At the international level, it is important that people take full advantage of this source of diversity by facilitating access for residents of each state and students of educational institutions of each country to the educational resources of other states. In particular, for higher education, it is extremely important for one country to recognize diplomas, degrees, and qualifications obtained in another country, which is one of the elements of the right to education and promotes the mobility of relationships between countries.

The priority task is to achieve the effectiveness of the functioning of the education system from the perspective of the social order of tomorrow, which includes problems of both the external efficiency of education and concerns, first of all, issues of its content,

and internal efficiency, which are associated with the organization of the management process.

Result

Education of the 21st century is designed to change the content and form of development necessary for the survival of civilization. The strategic goal of education as a social mechanism of self-organization today is to overcome the rapid development of social existence over social consciousness, the transition to the determining role of not material, but spiritual and cognitive values as we move towards a society based on knowledge. This process must be intelligently managed and contribute to the transformation of people's consciousness, which is possible as a result of changing the structure of the educational process, taking into account the need to purposefully design the future to realize its most favorable scenarios. The problem of assessing the role of the increased level of education of the workforce in the process of economic development has identified several approaches to its solution. There is a so-called concept of "human capital", the authors of which believe that the cost of the learning process is an "investment in a person", and the accumulation of knowledge and skills is the process of accumulating "human capi-

tal". In this case, the education system is seen as an "industry" that produces capital with a particularly long service life, since education provides a lifetime of income and the ability to participate in the spiritual life of society. The reasoning for this is that the capacity for economic activity is not given at birth, that just as the land is first cultivated and cultivated before it bears a harvest, so a person first requires training and education before he can be intelligently used in production.

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